

PastramiGate2 - SMBE edition

by Andrew Kern 2 years ago 69 Views ▾

Andrew Kern

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Anyone wanna play recreational accountant again? I took a lot of heat today for being naive, seems I wasn't alone in my naivety
1/24

8:53 PM - Mar 15, 2016

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Tonight I want to look at the tax reporting of [@OfficialSMBE](#), the society that publishes MBE and GBE 2/24

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Like [@PLoS](#) SMBE has been doing very well financially, but SMBE is much smaller. In 2012 they reported \$1.2M in revenue netting \$665K 3/24

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In 2013 SMBE reported \$1.8M in revenue and netted \$1.3M. Its worth noting that they posted a loss in 2011, but it looks like a typo?!? 4/24

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I'll focus on the [@OfficialSMBE](#) 2013 990 as I can't find 2014. There's actually very little to their tax filing in comparison to [@PLoS](#) 5/24

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[@OfficialSMBE](#) reported total assets of \$2.93MM, all held in cash. They made a tiny sum in what must be interest -- \$532 6/24

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[@OfficialSMBE](#) spent out \$568K, of that \$72K went to publishing the journals. Obviously this is at a totally different scale than [@PLOS](#) 7/24

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SMBE spent \$134K in travel, this is a much larger portion of revenue than what PLoS is spending. Paying tickets for meetings? 8/24

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[@OfficialSMBE](#) spent zero on advertising and lobbying. Okay onto the society specific stuff. This is where a big difference lies 9/24

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The number one expense for [@OfficialSMBE](#) SMBE in 2013 was their conference-- \$200K -- so a large percentage of revenue. 10/24

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[@OfficialSMBE](#) also spent \$28K on their Undergraduate Mentoring and Diversity Programming. Basically small awards to attend conference 11/24

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The final expense worth noting is grants-- @OfficialSMBE gave out \$60.5K in grants which included awards for 38 students 12/24

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All told then, @OfficialSMBE gave out \$88.5K or 6.8% of profits to postdocs, graduate students, and undergrads. Pretty darn neat IMO 13/24

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Its also worth noting that @OfficialSMBE is now sitting on a big chunk of money in cash (\$2.93MM). More awards? What's planned? 14/24

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The downside is that publishing OA with @OfficialSMBE is slightly more expensive than with PLoS 15/24

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GBE charges \$1800. If you were to compare this to @PLOSONE (perhaps a dubious comparison) @PLOSONE is cheaper at \$1495 16/24

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MBE charges \$2500, which is again more expensive than @PLOSgenetics (\$2250-- what got me into this mess to begin with...) 17/24

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These are presumably the economies of scale that @PLOS is developing 18/24

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BUT SMBE provides proofs and copy editors, so you aren't paying for the same level of service that you are at @PLOS 19/24

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So in short, prices are a bit more expensive for publishing at [@OfficialSMBE](#), but you are getting a bit of added value 20/24

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Further, and this is my bigger take home from the comparison, your grant money is going straight back to the community with SMBE 21/24

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You publish at slightly higher cost but that gets returned in form of meetings, awards, student development, child care grants, etc 22/24

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For me, I keep coming back to preferring the society model, even if it too is flawed. 23/24

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But as others have pointed out I'm naive and idealistic. I would like to see our grant money used for SCIENCE, not corporations
24/24

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Forgot to link out [@OfficialSMBE](#) tax documents:bit.ly/1SRx5uwbit.ly/1XtYkuCbit.ly/1nMYDV9

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Here's what [@OfficialSMBE](#) is planning on doing with their cash assets twitter.com/OfficialSMBE/s...

6:19 AM - Mar 16, 2016

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To be clear-- I am not attacking OA. OA is NECESSARY. My intent is to figure out where our pub charges go when we publish

6:41 AM - Mar 16, 2016

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